

OPTIMAL QUANTITY OF APPLICATION OF GLASS FIBER IN CONCRETE MIXTURE

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Abstract: In the article, studies and articles on the use of reinforced glass fiber reinforced concrete with high strength in the construction of buildings and structures are reviewed and analyzed.

Key words: fiberglass, concrete mix, strength, filler.

Introduction. There are very few studies on glass fiber reinforced concrete as a base material for building structural elements. In this article, recommendations are made for the construction industry to use this material as a base material to strengthen the structure

Research object: Concrete composite reinforced with glass fibers.

Concrete is the most widely used building material. The price of concrete is much cheaper than other materials. In this case, there is no material equivalent to concrete. That is, it includes materials that are available everywhere (locally). Another advantage is that concrete strength increases from year to year. This feature shows that concrete and reinforced concrete structures are durable for a long time. Concrete has many advantages as well as disadvantages. Concrete is an anisotropic (homogeneous) material, and one of its main disadvantages is low tensile strength.

Many properties of concrete depend on its density, that is, the density of concrete depends on the density of cement stone, the type of fillers and the structure of concrete. In the process of compacting the concrete mixture, it is necessary to ensure that the filler grains are maximally close to each other and their surface is completely covered with cement paste. An increase in the cement stone contact layer causes the formation of internal stresses during the crystallization process. As a result, the formation balance of the structure is disturbed. Fatigue occurs in places where the structure of the composition is not fully formed. This condition is quickly manifested on the surface of concrete and is characterized by the formation of microcracks.

A number of changes in the construction industry will significantly increase the demand for new materials. This makes it possible to create new types of concrete, which is the main construction material, using composite materials without changing the composition and properties of concrete [1].

From this point of view, answers to the questions of why to add fiberglass to the concrete mixture can be obtained:

- concrete shrinks less to highly variable loads;
- low humidity, less damage during freezing and thawing, and an increase in the number of periods of frost resistance directly increases the service life of structures;
- reduces water absorption of concrete and increases its resistance to wet environment;
- is resistant to the forces generated by friction;
- the state of plasticity improves;
- resistance increases.

Taking into account the above, it is recommended to include dispersed fibrous materials in the concrete mixture. Such dispersed fibers act as micro-reinforcements for the cement matrix and form a solid concrete by combining the constituents of the micro-matrix.

One of the fibrous materials used for microreinforcement of concrete and cement stone matrix is fiberglass. Their diameter is on average 13-15 μm , length 5-40 mm. High tensile strength (1500-3500 MPa), average density of 2.6 g/cm³.

High physical and mechanical properties of glass fibers expand its field of application.

The main physical and mechanical properties of glass fiber used in concrete reinforcement are presented in Table 1 [2].

General characteristics of fiberglass

Table 1

№	Indicators	Glass fiber
1	Fiber length, mm	5-40
2	Fiber diameter	13-15 μm
3	Stretching strength, MPa	1500-3500
4	Modulus of elasticity, GPa	70-80
5	Coefficient of elongation	4,5
6	Melting temperature, $^{\circ}\text{C}$	860
7	Alkali resistance	Low
8	Density, g/cm^3	2,6

Taking into account the above, experimental studies on the dispersion reinforcement of concrete with glass fibers were conducted.

PS400D20 cement of "Namangantsement" plant was used in this test. Cement has an actual density of $3.1 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$, bulk density of $1.33 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$, standard density of 14%, granularity of 8.2%, 28-day compressive strength of 34.4 MPa, flexural strength of 7.1 MPa, and specific surface area of $3000 - 3500 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$.

In the samples, the sand taken from the Namangan quarry, Toragorgan district, Namangan region, with a density of $1025 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$ and dimensions of 0-6 mm and moisture content of 3.1%, as a fine aggregate, and granite pebbles with a density of $815 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$ and grain sizes of 5-20 mm as a large aggregate. (sheben) were used. The appearance of the fine and coarse aggregates used for the cube-specimens is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Small and large fillers used in experimental research work

Figure 2. Appearances of glass fibers

The glass fibers produced by the Uzbek-German joint venture "Falk Porsche Fiberglass" located in the Almazor district of the city of Tashkent, Uzbekistan, shown in Figure 2 below, were used in these tests. The main indicators of fiberglass are presented in Table 2.

The main indicators of fiberglass

Table 2

Fiber type	Density g/cm ³	Modulus of elasticity, GPa	Tensile strength, MPa	Diameter mkm	Length, mm
Glass fiber	2,6	70-80	1500-3500	13-15	5, 10, 20, 25, 40

When measuring the amount of glass fibers, a scale of the "SF-400" model with high measurement accuracy was used. Experimental work was carried out in laboratory conditions to obtain B25 class concrete according to the design index by adding glass fibers to the concrete composition. This test

was conducted on the basis of regulatory indicators developed based on the requirements of the current international standard DAST 27006-2019, as shown in Table 2 below.

Table 3

General indicators of B25 class concrete

Concrete class in the project	Volumetric weight of concrete mixture, kg/m ³	Cement brand PS400D 20, kg	5-25mm Large filler (pebble), kg	0-6mm Fine filler (quartz sand), kg	water, l	Water/cement ratio
B25	2450	440	815	1025	180	0,41

Test samples were prepared in the construction-testing laboratory belonging to "Bunyodkor-3" LLC. Cube samples with sides of 100x100x100 mm were prepared in 6 series for conducting experiments.

Figure 4. Cube samples of concrete with glass fibers added

After the prepared samples were stored under normal conditions, they were removed from the molds, and the samples were marked and stored in a standard hardening chamber for 28 days. Cube samples prepared for testing are shown in Figure 4.

The samples were installed in the center of the lower plate of the press (Fig. 5). In the test, the amount of external load was continuously increased. The loading rate was 0.3-0.5 MPa/s. The compressive strength of concrete was calculated using the

following formula. $R = \frac{\alpha P}{A}$

where: R-breaking force, kg; *Figure 5. The process of testing cube samples*
A-cross-sectional area, cm²; α - sample-to-cube transfer coefficient

Analysis of experimental results: The main scientific results of practical importance were obtained in the experiments. Analyzes were carried out on them, included in the appropriate tables and graphs. Figure 6 shows the appearance of plain concrete cubes and fiberglass concrete cubes after testing.

Figure 6. General view after testing of cube specimens made of heavy concrete (a) and fiber concrete (b).

The results obtained through experimental tests of concrete cube samples prepared with and without glass fiber are shown in the form of a table.

28-day durability of cube specimens

Indicator	Fiberglass length	% of glass fiber in relation to the volume of concrete				
		0,1	0,2	0,3	0,4	0,5
		Compressive strength, MPa				
28 days durability	0	29,23				
	40	36,19	45,2	38,8	36,2	34,86

When the results of the research were studied using the method of dispersion-analysis of mathematical statistics, it was found that the effects of the percentage and length of the glass fiber added to the volume of the samples were significant.

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